

Crystal structure and magnetic properties of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ under multi-extreme conditions

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ABSTRACT

Structural and magnetic properties of the Shastry-Sutherland material $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ were studied in single-crystalline form under pressures up to 10 GPa, magnetic fields up to 17 T, and temperatures down to 0.3 K. Surprisingly robust magnetic order is observed with the Néel temperature $T_N = 2.1$ K stable up to 8.1 GPa. Indication of an additional magnetic phase formation can be traced in resistivity data for magnetic field along the c -axis exceeding the (pressure-dependent) metamagnetic transition. The related anomaly shifts to higher temperatures with increasing field, merging T_N at the tricritical point. Experiments with $\mu_0H // [110]$ revealed the pressure stabilization of observed magnetic phases with respect to the magnetic field. The crystal-structure type is stable up to 10 GPa, without any sign of symmetry change, exhibiting moderate volume compressibility with bulk modulus $B = 116(13)$ GPa, in good agreement with $B = 118$ GPa provided by the density functional theory.

INTRODUCTION

Magnetically frustrated systems attract special interest because of the possible formation of novel phases, which may become unstable under small variations of control parameters like a magnetic field, alloying, or external pressure. The impossibility of simultaneous satisfaction of interactions between spins through various exchange pathways gives rise to degenerate ground state spin structure which brings a great diversity of exotic phenomena. Magnetic analogs of liquid and ice given by frustration are sensitive even to slight perturbations that can induce instabilities in the system. The situation in which a small stimulus can have a tremendous consequence is vital for numerous prospective applications from information storage to magnetic refrigeration.

A simple realization of frustrated atomic arrangement is represented by the model of the two-dimensional Shastry-Sutherland lattice (SSL) [1]. Mutually orthogonal dimers of magnetic moments characterized by the intradimer interaction J are coupled via the interdimer interaction J' . Based on the ratio J'/J , one may distinguish between the two regimes, long-range antiferromagnetic (AFM) order preferred for larger J'/J , or spin-liquid (SL) state favored for smaller J'/J . The critical ratio of $J'/J \approx 0.6-0.7$ was theoretically predicted for the $T = 0$ limit [2-5]. At higher temperatures, the presence of intermediate phases (e.g. a plaquette state) is expected.

The archetypal SSL material is $\text{SrCu}_2(\text{BO}_3)_2$ adopting the tetragonal $I4_2m$ structure with the moment-bearing Cu^{2+} ($S = 1/2$) atoms arranged in the Shastry-Sutherland motif. The $J'/J = 0.64$ ratio results in the SL ground state formed by non-ordering dimers with the characteristic energy gap Δ between the singlet and triplet dimer states [6]. The application of moderate pressure was found to be an excellent tool for tuning the interactions to observe a gradual stabilization of long-range magnetic order. Above 2 GPa, the originally dimerized state is replaced by the plaquette state, followed by the formation of AFM order above 4 GPa [6,7]. On the opposite side, tetraborides RB_4 (e.g. with $R = \text{Tb}, \text{Er}, \text{Tm}$, [8-10])

were reported as the characteristic examples of gapless SSL systems exhibiting long-range magnetism with characteristic fractional magnetization plateaus in the AFM state. These compounds crystallize in a tetragonal $P4/mbm$ structure consisting of the R-layers alternated by B-layers along the crystallographic c -direction.

$\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$, presented within this study, crystallizes in a tetragonal $\text{U}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Sn}$ -type structure ($P4_2/mnm$), which is the distorted variant of $P4/mbm$, with the unit cell doubled along the c -direction forming two different Yb-networks [11]. The J and J' interactions are realized between the first and the second nearest Yb atoms in the basal plane. Details of the crystal structure are shown in Fig. 1. $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ represents an example of metallic Shastry-Sutherland material where both frustration and Kondo screening play important roles. This allows to examine the interplay between frustration and f -conduction electron hybridization and brings the potential to experimentally explore the universal phase diagram suggested for heavy-fermion compounds [11,12].

Fig. 1. (a) $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ unit cell, (b) c -axis projection with marked shortest (blue, Yb-dimers with exchange parameter J) and the second shortest (orange, interdimer exchange parameter J') Yb-Yb distances.

Similarly to RB_4 materials, $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ with $J'/J = 0.83$ belongs to the magnetically ordered SSL systems [13]. The Shastry-Sutherland frustration standing behind the formation of antiferromagnetic order ($T_N = 2.1$ K) from the liquid of uncoordinated dimers manifests by the weak entropy release at the ordering temperature less than $0.6 \times R \ln 2$ expected for the Kramers doublet, slow recovery of S above T_N , broad maximum in magnetic susceptibility between 2–3 K, as well as several characteristic magnetization steps appearing at low temperatures [11,13–17].

The physical properties of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ are highly anisotropic. The magnetization ratio between the basal plane and the crystallographic c -axis reaches 30. Within the square basal plane, the geometrical factor of $\sqrt{2}$ becomes decisive [14,18]. Complex magnetic phase diagrams (see Fig. 2) were reported for particular magnetic field orientations [15,16,18]. The simplest situation is found for $\mu_0 H // [001]$ with an almost field-independent onset of magnetic phase I at $T_N = 2.1$ K. In the case of $\mu_0 H // [100]$, the onset of phase I shifts to lower T with increasing field (suppressed around 2 T) and an additional phase II appears below 1 K surviving up to 4 T at the lowest T . The situation of $\mu_0 H // [110]$ resembles the combination of the two previous cases, modified again by the geometrical factor of $\sqrt{2}$. At $T_N = 2.1$ K, the field-independent transition to the magnetic phase III is observed, followed by phases I and II' at lower temperatures/higher fields. At $\mu_0 H = 0$ T, the phases I and III merge in a tricritical point.

Due to the strong Ising anisotropy, the magnetic moments are constrained to lie in the $[110]$ and $[-110]$ directions, perpendicular to the dimer bonds, forming two independent orthogonal sublattices [16,19]. The zero-field antiferromagnetic structure of phase I is formed by a $5 \times 5 \times 1$ magnetic supercell based on $[110]$ and $[-110]$ stripes consisting of single dimer types, with the two Yb planes coupled antiferromagnetically along the c -axis [19]. Magnetic field applied along the basal-plane diagonal $[110]$ polarizes the moments parallel to the field, while the perpendicular moments

remain unaffected. Phase III corresponds to the state with completely suppressed order in the field-aligned sublattice. The phase II (II') was ascribed to the pseudospin-flop state stabilized by multipole interaction [16]. While both sublattices are equally polarized in phase II (field along [100]-direction), only the sublattice with moments parallel to the field has substantial magnetization in phase II' (field along [110]-direction).

Fig. 2. Phase diagram of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ at ambient pressure for magnetic field applied along the [100], [110], and [001] crystallographic directions in (a), (b), and (c), respectively, constructed by the combination of previously published data [15,16,18].

In the present work, we describe experimental results of high-pressure studies of crystal structure and transport properties, providing insight in pressure and field variations of magnetic properties. The results are compared with other known cases of regular and anomalous rare earths in very similar structure arrangement.

EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

Single-crystalline samples of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ were prepared following the Pb self-flux growth procedure described in [11]. Pure elements (Yb 3N, Pt 5N, Pb 5N) were weighed in the atomic ratio Yb:Pt:Pb = 5:4:40, inserted into the alumina crucible, and sealed in the silica glass under the protective argon atmosphere. Fast heating to 1180 °C (kept for 4 hours) was followed by a 7 °C/hr continuous temperature decrease down to 450 °C where the remaining Pb-flux was centrifuged. Needle-shaped single crystals (length of several mm, cross-section in the order of $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, long edge oriented along the crystallographic c -direction) were further treated by the solution of acetic acid to get rid of the surface contamination by Pb. In such a way, single crystals of pure and homogenous composition were obtained, verified by EDX analysis (Yb:Pt:Pb = 2:2:1 with variations less than 1 %) and powder X-ray diffraction (one piece of crystal was crushed).

The impact of high pressure on electrical transport was studied for two orientations of the sample with respect to the direction of magnetic field, using two different types of pressure cells. A double-layer cylindrical pressure cell with a nominal pressure range of up to 3 GPa, [20], was employed for measurements in a longitudinal setup with the electrical current parallel to the external magnetic field, applied along the c -axis, i.e. [001]. Daphne oil 7474 with a broad range of hydrostaticity and known pressure drop of 0.3 GPa between the room temperature and low- T region, [21], was used as a pressure-transmitting medium. The pressure was determined at room temperature using a thermally stabilized manganin wire. In the case of the magnetic field oriented in the basal-plane direction [110], a diamond anvil cell (DAC) was used. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 3, with 4 thin Au wires arranged in the van der Pauw configuration press-attached to the sample. As a pressure-transmitting medium, NaCl was used in this case. The pressure was determined using the ruby fluorescence method (several ruby balls were loaded together with the sample into the sample space).

Experiments cover a broad range of temperatures and magnetic fields. The cryomagnet equipped with a large superconducting coil and the cryopump-controlled ^3He insert allowing to reach the field of ≈ 18 T and temperatures down to 0.3 K was used for c -axis-field experiments. For measurements in the $\mu_0 H // [110]$ arrangement, the 9 T Cryomagnet equipped with a dilution refrigerator (Leiden Cryogenics) was used.

In order to estimate the pressure impact on the crystal lattice, a high-pressure XRD experiment was carried out. We used selected small grains from the sample crushed for ambient pressure XRD. The grain size was $10\ \mu\text{m}$ to avoid any preferential orientation effect related to the restricted sample space. The powder was loaded in the diamond anvil cell (DAC, Almax design [22], culet diameter of $500\ \mu\text{m}$). We used a steel gasket with a drilled hole of $200\ \mu\text{m}$ and Daphne oil 7373, [23,24], as a pressure-transmitting medium. The pressure was determined using the ruby fluorescence method, similarly to the high- p resistivity measurement mentioned above. XRD patterns were collected using the diffractometer Rigaku R-axis Rapid II with the Mo-tube X-ray source and a cylindrical image plate detector. A $100\ \mu\text{m}$ collimator was used to optimize the signal from the sample and to avoid the contribution of the steel gasket to the diffraction patterns. Experimental data were integrated from the 2D detector into $I(2\theta)$ dependence and resulting 1D patterns were fitted using FullProf software [25].

Fig. 3. (a) DAC sample space with the setup for measurements of electrical resistance, (b) DAC sample space with the powder of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ for X-ray diffraction (the inset shows the ruby fluorescence technique of pressure determination).

The general potential (Linearized) Augmented Plane Waves plus local orbitals ((L)APW+lo) method, [26], was used to solve Kohn-Sham equations for DFT, convenient due to the low crystal symmetry of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$. The calculations were done within the Local Density Approximation (LDA, [27]) and three types of exchange-correlation potential within the Generalized Gradient Approximations, namely GGA-PBE [28], GGA-PBESOL [29], and GGA-WC [30]. The Ytterbium $4f$ states were treated as Bloch states and open-core atomic-like states in order to check both limits of $4f$ -electron behavior. Several k -meshes in the Brillouin zone were involved to ensure the convergence of charge density, total energy, Fermi energy, electric field gradient, and density of states at the Fermi level. The (L)APW+lo method provides only (velocity/velocity of light)² corrections derived from the Dirac equation for relativistic treatment of valence electrons. From various GGA methods available, the (L)APW+lo method was applied to determine equilibrium volume and to compare with the experimental value. More than 2800 basis functions ($RK_{\text{max}} = 7, 8, 9$; more than 140 basis functions per atom) were used to obtain converge results as was suggested by Schwarz [31]. The maximum number of augmented atomic functions inside the spheres was governed by $LMAX = 10$. The charge density was represented by plane waves in the interstitial region and therefore was expanded using $G_{\text{max}} = 16$ (default value is $G = 12$). So the calculations of equilibrium volume include velocity mass and Darwin corrections (scalar relativistic mode, [26]) to minimize the forces at Yb and Pt positions and the corresponding total energy for each change of volume.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurements of electrical resistivity were chosen as a suitable and technically feasible probe to analyze the magnetism of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ under multi-extreme conditions, covering high pressures, high magnetic fields, and low temperatures.

The temperature dependence of electrical resistivity $\rho(T)$ is non-monotonous, reflecting the Kondo lattice state based on the magnetic $4f^{13}$ state. While the magnetic ordering manifests as a precipitous drop of resistivity, there is an extended temperature range above T_N with a negative resistivity coefficient, associated with the Kondo interaction of conduction electrons with the local moments of Yb. As a result of the interplay of the single-ion Kondo interaction and the formation of a coherent state just above T_N , a broad maximum is formed around $T = 6$ K.

Fig. 4 shows the temperature dependencies of electrical resistance measured at various pressures applied without external magnetic field. The data obtained in both types of experiments are shown to depict the pressure-driven changes of resistance in the whole pressure range. The results suggest very strong stability of the magnetic phase I with ambient-pressure onset at $T_N = 2.1$ K almost unaffected by pressure up to 8.1 GPa. Only very weak broadening of the anomaly is noticeable at elevated pressures, however the transition temperature itself remains practically pinned to 2.1 K.

The increase of the resistivity values in the broad maximum is suggestive of the strengthening of Kondo interactions. Similar behavior was observed e.g. in $\text{Ce}_2\text{Pd}_2\text{In}$, where the pressure-driven onset of the strong Kondo effect stands behind the loss of magnetism [32,33]. Also the Ce-analog $\text{Ce}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ was reported to be a heavy-fermion antiferromagnet [34].

However, one has to keep in mind that despite the similarity of the Kondo regime, the underlying tendencies are opposite for Yb and Ce. On a large scale, volume compression suppresses magnetism for Ce systems due to the lower volume of the non-magnetic $4f^0$ state, which starts to be admixed into the magnetic $4f^1$ state. For Yb, the tendency is just the opposite – admixture of the non-magnetic $4f^{14}$ state suppresses magnetism upon volume expansion. This can be demonstrated on the $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pd}_2\text{Sn}$ -

$\text{Yb}_2\text{Pd}_2\text{In}$ system with non-magnetic terminal phases, in which the volume tuning by concentrations and/or pressures can induce magnetism [35]. On the other hand, magnetism does not appear in volume-expanded hydride $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pd}_2\text{Sn}$ [36].

Besides the general tendencies related to the variable $4f$ occupancy and the Kondo state, there are naturally also crystal-field phenomena affecting the magnetic properties, and in case of geometrical frustration, which can occur at this structure type, there is additional route of possible breakdown of magnetism.

While the interplay of the magnetic frustration and heavy-fermion behavior opens the playground for investigation of the general phase diagram suggested for heavy-fermion materials [12], the magnetism of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ remains stable.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of zero-field ($\mu_0H = 0$ T) electrical resistance measured at selected pressure points in (a) double-layer piston pressure cell, (b, c) diamond anvil cell, (c) depicts the formation of Kondo maximum at elevated pressures.

The properties of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ are highly anisotropic. The impact of magnetic fields oriented along the crystallographic direction [001], the c -axis, is visible in Fig. 5. In moderate magnetic fields, only a very weak effect on electrical resistance is observed. On the other hand, at higher magnetic fields (at $\mu_0H_{\text{MM}} \approx 13$ T at ambient pressure, [15]), the metamagnetic transition appears, accompanied by the sharp anomaly on the magnetoresistance data (Fig. 5(a), data obtained at $T = 0.4$ K). At magnetic fields exceeding μ_0H_{MM} , the transition temperature T_N is gradually suppressed, while the additional anomaly (the second kink below the linear part of the data) appears at lower temperatures, shifting to higher T with increasing field. Based on these findings, we can argue that the ferromagnetic (FM) or polarized paramagnetic (PPM) component with magnetic moments oriented in the c -direction is formed above μ_0H_{MM} . Application of pressure results first in a relatively fast (linear) decrease of μ_0H_{MM} , which can be discussed in the sense of the lattice compression supporting the formation of the additional field-aligned component. However, at $p > 1.25$ GPa, the metamagnetic field starts to saturate around $\mu_0H_{\text{MM}} \approx 9$ T.

The situation for $p = 1.7$ GPa is shown in Fig. 5(b). The metamagnetic transition appears at $\mu_0H_{\text{MM}}(1.7 \text{ GPa}) \approx 9.8$ T. Below μ_0H_{MM} , no significant change in temperature dependencies of electrical resistivity is observed, while the further increase of magnetic field leads to the strengthening of the FM (PPM) component resulting in merging of both anomalies at the field of the tricritical point, estimated as $\mu_0H_{\text{TCP}} \approx 20$ T.

Fig. 5. (a) Pressure dependence of the metamagnetic-transition field $\mu_0 H_{MM}$ (the inset displays the magnetoresistance curves, with a vertically offset for better readability), data obtained at $T = 0.4$ K, the orange symbol corresponds to the value presented in [15], (b) field effect on the temperature dependencies of electrical resistance measured at $p = 1.70$ GPa (an offset of 0.2 is used for individual curves, the star symbols represent the positions of the additional anomaly).

The phase diagram with the magnetic field applied along the [110]-direction is more complex [16,18]. The magnetic phase I is suppressed (from the initial 2.1 K) in moderate magnetic fields (of 1 T), the additional magnetic phase II' is formed at low temperatures (below 1 K) in the limited field range of 1.0–2.2 T, while the almost field-independent transition remaining at 2.1 K corresponds to the formation of the state III (at zero field the transition merges with the onset of I).

In order to track the pressure-driven changes of the phase diagram, temperature dependencies of electrical resistance at constant values of magnetic field (up to 6 T), and the isothermal field dependencies (at temperatures down to 0.3 K) were measured. Temperature dependencies are dominated by the presence of the 2.1 K ordering temperature (slightly shifting to higher temperatures in fields exceeding 1.5 T), while the other two transitions are barely noticeable. It appears that much more convenient and convincing is to analyze the anomalies in $R(\mu_0 H)$ data to follow the pressure impact on these low-temperature transitions. Magnetoresistance measured at selected temperatures and pressures is summarized in Fig. 6.

Both transitions are shifted to higher fields when applying pressure. Moreover, the region of magnetic phase II', i.e. the field range between the arrows marking the individual transitions, broadens. In that sense, both magnetic phases I and II' are more resistant at higher pressures with respect to magnetic fields. Increasing the temperature above 1 K results in the merging of both transitions followed by the gradual shift to lower magnetic fields, in agreement with the previously reported phase diagrams, almost irrespective of applied pressure. Reviewing the data, one may notice a more emphasized low-field anomaly (inflection point) at 3 K, which may suggest that the magnetic order survives to the higher temperatures when pressure is applied.

Fig. 6. Temperature variations of magnetoresistance data obtained at various pressures. The arrows mark the magnetic transitions between phases I and II', and II' and III, respectively. The data in the last two panels are rescaled to fit the overall scheme.

It seems that much more important for the magnetic properties of $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$, compared to the effects related to the Shastry-Sutherland frustration, is the strong magnetic anisotropy. While pressure does not affect the onset of magnetic order (i.e. the impact of pressure on the decisive ingredients for Shastry-Sutherland frustration is negligible, it is, the J'/J ratio remains probably unaffected, the SSL motif unchanged, and the spin-liquid state of Yb-dimers is not pressure-supported/suppressed), the clear pressure-dependent preference of individual magnetic phases is evident. The results are summarized in the phase diagram (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Cross-section of the temperature-field-pressure phase diagram of Yb_2Pt_2Pb constructed at $T = 0.3$ K for magnetic field applied along [110]-direction. The individual points were taken from the magnetoresistance data presented in Fig. 6.

Unfortunately, the availability of high-pressure experimental data on other Shastry-Sutherland materials is very limited. Interesting results were achieved studying magnetic properties of the SSL system $SrCu_2(BO_3)_2$, where the application of pressure leads to destabilization of the dimer state and formation of the plaquette state ($p > 2$ GPa) followed by the onset of long-range antiferromagnetic order ($p > 4$ GPa). On the other hand, no study of the pressure impact on the ordered SSL systems has been reported yet and any comparison is thus not possible. However, based on the mechanism of Shastry-Sutherland frustration, the resulting behavior strongly depends on the layout of magnetic interactions in the lattice and thus the effect of pressure will be specific for each compound without the possibility of any general prediction. Crucial is the anisotropy of lattice compression, since the strength of magnetic interaction between particular magnetic atoms depends directly on their distances. In the case of metallic R-based materials, the exchange is realized typically by RKKY (Ruderman-Kittel-Kasuya-Yosida) interaction and also the sign of the interaction may change along the radial distance from the given atom, making the situation even more complex.

Ambient-pressure XRD pattern can be described by U_2Pt_2Sn -model (space group $P4_2/mnm$) with the lattice parameters $a = 7.755(11)$ Å and $c = 7.007(12)$ Å, resulting in the unit-cell volume $V_0 = 421(1)$ Å³. The experimental equilibrium volume V_0 can be compared with the results of LDA and GGA methods. Ratio V/V_0 comes out 2.1% smaller than V_0 using LDA functional. This is a typical overbinding with full potential calculations [37]. On the other hand, calculations with frequently used GGA-PBE, [28], underbinds by 4.8%. The GGA-PBESOL, [29], and GGA-WC, [30], results of V/V_0 are 0.6% and 1.2% smaller, respectively. Thus, semilocal GGA-PBESOL exchange-correlation functional improves the agreement of calculated V with V_0 but neither functional is perfect for Yb_2Pt_2Pb . Surprisingly the overall performance of used exchange correlation functionals does not change if the itinerant Bloch $4f$ -states are used instead of the open-core treatment of $4f$ -states.

The evolution of diffraction patterns with hydrostatic pressure is seen in Fig. 8. The gradual shift of diffraction peaks reflects the lattice compression. The U_2Pt_2Sn -type crystal structure remains stable at least up to 10 GPa. Lattice parameters obtained by Rietveld fitting of experimental data together with calculated unit-cell volume ($V_{u.c.} = a^2 \times c$) as functions of pressure are shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8. Pressure dependence of X-ray diffraction patterns together with the fit to the U_2Pt_2Sn -type of tetragonal structure (space group $P4_2/mnm$, shown for the lowest and the highest applied pressure). The inset shows a gradual shift of diffraction peaks in the selected angle range (15° – 23°).

Pressure dependence of $V_{u.c.}$ (see Fig. 9(a)) obeys the Murnaghan equation of states (EOS)

$$V = V_0(1 + B'p/B_0)^{-1/B'} \quad (1)$$

with the equilibrium bulk modulus $B_0 = 1/k_V = 116(13)$ GPa and its p derivative $B' = 8.6$. These values are in very good agreement with $B_0 = 118$ GPa and $B' = 4.8$ provided by the density-functional theory (DFT) calculations assuming $4f$ electrons localized (open core treatment). Treating the $4f$ -states as itinerant Bloch states provides $B = 98$ GPa, which is significantly lower than the experimental value. The obtained experimental values of B are slightly higher but still comparable to the data available for the $P4_2/mnm$ analogs (e.g. La_2Pd_2In , Ce_2Pd_2In , or Tm_2Cu_2In with $B_0 = 48, 82,$ and 74 GPa, respectively [33,38,39]). Relatively soft lattices of these 221 materials make them particularly interesting due to possibly easy tuning of physical properties in accessible conditions.

The effect of pressure on both lattice parameters a and c is comparable, as shown in Fig. 9(b). Such low anisotropy of cohesion properties is rather unusual. The situation of a softer a -parameter, attributed to additional degrees of freedom in the basal plane (variable orientation of the square

motives of R and T atoms) presented for several R_2T_2X materials with $P4/mbm$ crystal structure [33,38] is not reproduced here. Although the mutual arrangement of R atoms, as well as of T atoms, is in principle identical, there is another free fractional coordinate in the c -direction, making the situation different in the two related structure types.

Fig. 9. (a) Pressure dependence of unit-cell volume $V_{\text{u.c.}}$ fitted by Murnaghan equation of states (1) together with the data obtained from density functional theory calculations, and (b) pressure variations of lattice parameters a and c (the same y -axis range is chosen in both parts of the figure).

The fact that the onset of long-range magnetic order remains unaffected at pressures up to 8.1 GPa means either that the magnetic ordering itself is very robust (and the preceding spin-liquid state cannot be strengthened in this pressure range, and/or the changes in J'/J ratio are not sufficient to have a significant impact), or that the lattice compresses in such a way, that the ratio of the first and the second nearest-neighbor Yb distances (and thus the related interactions) remains unaffected. Analysis of the pressure impact on particular atomic distances within the unit cell is unfortunately beyond the limits of the used experimental technique.

Such situation is contrasting with the pressure-triggered magnetic frustration in $\text{Ce}_2\text{Pd}_2\text{In}$. In this material, only a slightly lower magnetic moment can be found as an ambient-pressure sign of potential frustration, but the pressure of $\approx 4\text{--}6$ GPa leads to the formation of equilateral triangles (i.e. the strong geometrically-frustrated atomic arrangement) of Ce (AFM-coupled) atoms accompanied by the complete suppression of magnetic ordering.

CONCLUSION

Unlike similar cerium analog in $\text{Ce}_2\text{Pd}_2\text{In}$ with $4f$ moments in principle sensitive to volume compression, the $4f^{13}$ states of Yb^{3+} cannot be destabilized by pressure. However, there could still be effects of pressure on magnetic frustration. Despite that, the Shastry-Sutherland material $\text{Yb}_2\text{Pt}_2\text{Pb}$ was found to exhibit a high stability of the magnetically ordered state up to pressures of 8.1 GPa, without any significant effect on the ordering temperature at $T_N = 2.1$ K. Pressure impact on the magnetic phase diagrams with respect to the orientation of the magnetic field was studied. The signs of the new magnetic phase formation above the (pressure-dependent) metamagnetic transition were revealed in the case of the c -axis magnetic field. The related anomaly shifts to higher T with increasing field resulting in the suppression of the initial magnetic state (phase I) at the tricritical point. In the

case of $\mu_0 H // [110]$, both phases I and II' were found to be stabilized (with respect to the magnetic field) by the application of pressure.

The crystal structure remains stable up to 10 GPa. The bulk modulus was found to be $B = 116(13)$ GPa, in very good agreement with $B = 118$ GPa provided by the first-principles DFT calculations.

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